

Initiate2 Drill Testing Questionnaire

Initiate2 is an initiative, designed by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the World Food Programme (WFP), which aims to bring together emergency actors, research and academic institutions, and international and national partners to work together on technical solutions that will contribute to public health, individual care and operational field research.

The first innovation designed by Initiate2 is the Infectious Disease Treatment Module (IDTM), a rapidly deployable, easily transportable, extendable, self-contained and self-sufficient treatment module for infectious diseases irrespective of the mode of transmission. Such a solution, built on field experience, will not replace current facilities but rather integrate them by enabling responders to safely provide high quality care from the onset of the emergency, whilst more permanent and complex structures are set up.

If you are reading this document, it is because you have been invited to participate in the IDTM drill. The purpose of this drill exercise is to test the utility of IDTM in multiple medical situations and to test logistic requirements relating to set-up, transportation, cleaning, and take-down. From the feedback provided the product will be assessed relating to key design principles defined by the Initiate2 stakeholders, which are as follows; contact-enabling design, accessibility and inclusiveness, cultural adaptability and participation, constructability, adaptability and infection prevention and control (IPC), usability, and transportability.

The drill will be composed of different scenarios which will allow us to test the design principles against simulated interventions. At the end of each scenario, your opinions will be collected through this structured survey questionnaire. The data collected will then be used to improve the IDTM prototype and potentially used for external publications.

1. I consent to my responses being used in a published study and have signed an informed consent form confirming this. *

Yes

No

Your Information

2. Please choose your pseudonymization Code, which you use for all the coming questionnaires according to the following instructions:

First digit: First letter of mother's first name (e.g. **L**uise)

Second character: Second letter of father's first name (e.g. H**A**ns)

Third digit: Third letter of the own month of birth (e.g. 14. Ma**R**ch)

Fourth digit: Last letter of own birthplace (e.g. Bon**N**)

Example: **LARN** *

3. Gender *

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

4. Age (in full years) *

5. Nationality (Please use the International country abbreviation) *

6. Years of Experience in the Humanitarian or Medical Sector (in full years) *

7. Select the pillar that best describes your current profile

*

- Nurse
- Medical Doctor
- Coordinator
- Logistician
- WASH specialist
- Architect
- IPC Specialist
- Laboratory
- Supply
- Epidemiologist
- Sonstiges

Medical Scenario 1

Scenario description: Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 5 in hospitalization. During lunch, the patient shows signs of difficulty in breathing.

Hypothesis we are testing: The patient is attended and treated in real-time within critical incidents

Success indicator: Adequate treatment can be provided to all patient groups. Visibility and physical contact is possible according to IPC measures.

8. The medical team was able to attend to the patient within adequate time. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

9. Any comments on the assessment above?

10. The medical team was able to provide adequate treatment in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

11. Any comments on the assessment above?

12. It was possible for the medical team to use the medical kits correctly within the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

13. Any comments on the assessment above?

14. It was possible for the medical team to properly move and have access to the patient within the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

15. Any comments on the assessment above?

16. The hypothesis "the patient is attended and treated in real time within critical incidents" was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

17. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 2

Scenario description: Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed pathogen X (airborne transmission) through PCR on day 5 in hospitalization. One physician and one nurse prepared a dose of mAb114 and are currently infusing the patient. Suddenly, the patient develops pyrexia, chills, tachycardia and tachypnoea.

Hypothesis we are testing: The patient is attended and treated in real-time within critical incidents

Success indicator: Critical incident is identified quickly Patient is attended within adequate time. Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time. It is possible to use medical kits correctly within the IDTM.

18. The medical team was able to attend to the patient within adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

19. Any comments on the assessment above?

20. The medical team was able to provide adequate treatment in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

21. Any comments on the assessment above?

22. It was possible for the medical team to use the medical kits correctly within the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

23. Any comments on the assessment above?

24. The transparent screen was comfortable to use. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

25. Any comments on the assessment above?

26. The transparent screen was intuitive *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

27. Any comments on the assessment above?

28. The transparent screen enabled sufficient communication (e.g. hearing & speaking to others through the screen) *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

29. Any comments on the assessment above?

30. The hypothesis "the patient is attended and treated in real time within critical incidents" was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

31. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 3

Scenario description: Patient is brought to the isolation unit together with his mother, both suspect of infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission). Has had dyspnea and coughing for 2 days.

Hypothesis we are testing: IDTM is adaptable for all age groups (i.e. Newborn - Children - Adult - Elderly) with their special needs. Visual and physical (i.e. in wall integrated gloves) contact to relatives is possible.

Success indicator: Adequate treatment can be provided to all patient groups. Visibility and physical contact is possible according to IPC measures.

32. Adequate treatment was able to be provided to all patient groups

*

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

33. Any comments on the assessment above?

34. Visibility and physical contact was possible according to IPC measures. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

35. Any comments on the assessment above?

36. The hypothesis "IDTM is adaptable for all age groups (i.e. Newborn - Children - Adult - Elderly) with their special needs. Visual and physical (i.e. in wall integrated gloves) contact to relatives is possible" was supported by this test *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

37. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 4

Scenario description: Patient had contact to a patient with pathogen X on a funeral. Since 2 days mild symptoms fever, headache, muscle pain

Hypothesis we are testing: The IDTM can receive an ambulance with a patient that is ambulatory (note: no clinical emergency).

Success indicator: The ambulance is successfully received, including decontamination of the ambulance (prep. for next transport) and a patient is successfully screened, triaged and admitted in the IDTM.

38. The ambulance was successfully received, including decontamination of the ambulance and preparation for next transport *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

39. Any comments on the assessment above?

40. The patient was able to be successfully screened, triaged and admitted in the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

41. Any comments on the assessment above?

42. The hypothesis "The IDTM can receive an ambulance with a patient that is ambulatory" was supported by this test *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

43. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 5

Scenario description: Patient had contact with a patient with pathogen X at the funeral of his wife. The last 2 days they have had moderate symptoms with fever, headache, muscle pain, and since today they have general fatigue and dizziness

Hypothesis we are testing: The IDTM can receive an ambulance and receive a non-ambulatory patient (i.e. arriving on a stretcher) simultaneously.

Success indicator: The ambulance is successfully received, including decontamination of the ambulance (prep. for next transport) and a patient arriving on a stretcher is successfully screened, triaged and admitted in the IDTM.

44. The ambulance was successfully received, including decontamination of the ambulance and preparation for next transport *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

45. Any comments on the assessment above?

46. A non-walking patient was able to be successfully screened, triaged and admitted in the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

47. Any comments on the assessment above?

48. The hypothesis "The IDTM can receive an ambulance and receive a non-ambulatory patient simultaneously" was supported by this test *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

49. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 6

Scenario description: Patient had contact with a patient with pathogen X. He was a former soldier. For 4 days he has had moderate symptoms with coughing, fever, headache, muscle pain

Hypothesis we are testing: An agitated patient can be managed from the screening area to the patient room whilst maintaining conditions for staff safety.

Success indicator: Safety for staff is provided. No contamination of any staff-members. No injuries to any staff-members. No contamination / injuries to other patients. Patient is stabilized / calmed down with adequate treatment (talk down / medication). Enough spacing for movement of staff from screening to patient room is provided.

50. Safety for the staff was provided in the IDTM (E.g. No contamination of any staff-members, no injuries to any staff-members). *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

51. Any comments on the assessment above?

52. There was no risk of contamination or injuries to other patients *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

53. Any comments on the assessment above?

54. The patient was able to be stabilized / calmed down with adequate treatment (talk down / medication) *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

55. Any comments on the assessment above?

56. There was enough spacing for movement of staff from the screening to the patient room *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

57. Any comments on the assessment above?

58. The hypothesis "An agitated patient can be managed from the screening area to the patient room whilst maintaining conditions for staff safety" was supported by this test *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

59. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 7

Scenario description: Patient with pathogen X. Since 10 days in the IDTM with severe ARDS, intubated, prone positioning and supportive treatment. Since he is getting better, the sedation is paused to evaluate his neurological status.

Hypothesis we are testing: An agitated patient can be managed under safe conditions for the staff in the patient room.

Success indicator: Staff accessing the patient room in adequate time. Safety for staff is provided. No contamination of any staff-members. No injuries to any staff-members. No contamination / injuries to other patients. Patient is stabilized / calmed down with adequate treatment (talk down / medication). Enough spacing for staff is provided

60. The staff could access the patient room in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

61. Any comments on the assessment above?

62. There was no risk of contamination or injuries to other patients *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

63. Any comments on the assessment above?

64. The patient was able to be stabilized / calmed down with adequate treatment (talk down / medication) *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

65. Any comments on the assessment above?

66. There was enough spacing for movement of staff from the screening to the patient room *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

67. Any comments on the assessment above?

68. The hypothesis "An agitated patient can be managed under safe conditions for the staff in the patient room" was supported by this test *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

69. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 8

Scenario description: Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 7 in quarantine. Intubated and renal replacement therapy für AKI for 6 days. Due to ARDS prone positioning for 2 days. Patient in prone position.

Hypothesis we are testing: Patient care can continue to be provided during power break-downs due to disruptive phenomena.

Success indicator: Power-Backup and Oxygen-Backup for critical infrastructure (respirator / monitoring) is working on time. Staff can move in adequate time from green to red area to provide patient care.

70. The staff could access the patient room in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

71. Any comments on the assessment above?

72. The Power-Backup and Oxygen-Backup for critical infrastructure (respirator / monitoring) was able to start working on time. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

73. Any comments on the assessment above?

74. The staff was able to move from the green to the red area to provide patient care within adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

75. Any comments on the assessment above?

76. The hypothesis "Patient care can continue to be provided during power breakdowns due to disruptive phenomena." was supported by this test *

Strongly
Disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly
Agree

77. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 9

Scenario description: Pregnant patient (32nd week of pregnancy, 3rd pregnancy), comes to the unit with high fever, difficulty breathing, general body pain and begin of labor. Patient was brought to the isolation room. Already in expulsion stage of birth.

Hypothesis we are testing: The IDTM is able to accommodate a small theater and neonatal resuscitation unit within the module, if required.

Success indicator: Mother and neonate survival after labor and neonatal resuscitation. No nosocomial infection for HCW (through secretions, airborne or even accident/incidents within the room), enough room space to perform the procedures. Adaptation of the module to a theater and neonatal unit is possible.

78. There was enough space to perform the necessary procedures. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

79. Any comments on the assessment above?

80. Adaptation of the module to a theater and neonatal unit was possible. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

81. Any comments on the assessment above?

82. The hypothesis "The IDTM is able to accommodate a small theater and neonatal resuscitation unit within the module, if required." was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

83. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 10

Scenario description: Pregnant patient (39th week of pregnancy, 2nd pregnancy), came to the unit with high fever, difficulty breathing, general body pain and begin of labor. Isolated as suspected. Child was born 10 minutes ago, vaginal birth without abnormalities.

Hypothesis we are testing: The IDTM is able to accommodate a small theater and neonatal resuscitation unit within the module, if required.

Success indicator: Mother and neonate survival after labor and neonatal resuscitation. No nosocomial infection for HCW (through secretions, airborne or even accident/incidents within the room), enough room to perform the procedures. Adaptation module to a theater and neonatal unit.

84. There was enough space to perform the necessary procedures. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

85. Any comments on the assessment above?

86. Adaptation of the module to a theater and neonatal unit was possible. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

87. Any comments on the assessment above?

88. The hypothesis "The IDTM is able to accommodate a small theater and neonatal resuscitation unit within the module, if required." was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

89. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 11

Scenario description: Pregnant patient (39th week of pregnancy, 4th pregnancy), came to the unit with high fever, difficulty breathing, general body pain and beginning of labor. She was isolated as a suspected case. Suspicion of fetal distress with fetal bradycardia -> Decision to do a Cesarean section.

Hypothesis we are testing: The IDTM is able to accommodate a small theater and neonatal resuscitation unit within the module, if required.

Success indicator: Mother and neonate survival after labor and neonatal resuscitation. No nosocomial infection for HCW (through secretions, airborne or even accident/incidents within the room), enough room space to perform the procedures. Adaptation module to a theater and neonatal unit.

90. There was enough space to perform the necessary procedures. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

91. Any comments on the assessment above?

92. Adaptation of the module to a theater and neonatal unit was possible. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

93. Any comments on the assessment above?

94. The hypothesis "The IDTM is able to accommodate a small theater and neonatal resuscitation unit within the module, if required." was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

95. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 12

Scenario description: The Patient is admitted after contact with an infected patient at a funeral. Sore throat for 5 days, fever, and increasing dyspnea since today.

Hypothesis we are testing: The patient can be attended and treated in real-time within critical incident

Success indicator: Critical incident is identified quickly Patient is attended within adequate time. Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time. Medical Management kits are used correctly

96. The critical incident was identified and the patient was attended to quickly *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

97. Any comments on the assessment above?

98. Adequate treatment was provided in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

99. Any comments on the assessment above?

100. It was possible to use the necessary medical kits correctly within the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

101. Any comments on the assessment above?

102. The hypothesis "The patient can be attended and treated in real-time within critical incident." was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

103. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 13

Scenario description:

Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 15 in quarantine. Intensified respiratory therapy (endotracheal intubated) for 5 days. In the last 20 minutes the oxygen saturation is dropping.

Hypothesis we are testing: The patient can be attended and treated in real-time within critical incident

Success indicator: Critical incident is identified quickly Patient is attended within adequate time. Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time. Medical Management kits are used correctly

104. The critical incident was identified and the patient was attended to quickly *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

105. Any comments on the assessment above?

106. Adequate treatment was provided in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

107. Any comments on the assessment above?

108. It was possible to use the necessary medical kits correctly within the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

109. Any comments on the assessment above?

110. The hypothesis "The patient can be attended and treated in real-time within critical incident." was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

111. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 14

Scenario description: Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 15 in hospitalization. Intensified respiratory therapy was performed for 10 days. Extubating was possible 2 days ago. Since today patient has increasingly reduced general condition with disturbance of consciousness.

Hypothesis we are testing: The patient can be attended and treated in real-time within critical incident

Success indicator: Critical incident is identified quickly. Patient is attended within adequate time. Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time. Medical Management kits are used correctly.

112. The critical incident was identified and the patient was attended to quickly *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

113. Any comments on the assessment above?

114. Adequate treatment was provided in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

115. Any comments on the assessment above?

116. It was possible to use the necessary medical kits correctly within the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

117. Any comments on the assessment above?

118. The hypothesis "The patient can be attended and treated in real-time within critical incident." was supported by this test. *

Strongly
Disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly
Agree

119. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 15

Scenario description: Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 5 in hospitalization. Current pregnancy at 33 weeks of gestation. Complains of headache, dizziness, fatigue since 2 hours.

Hypothesis we are testing: The patient can be attended and treated in real-time within critical incident

Success indicator: Critical incident is identified quickly. Patient is attended within adequate time. Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time. Medical Management kits are used correctly.

120. The critical incident was identified and the patient was attended to quickly *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

121. Any comments on the assessment above?

122. Adequate treatment was provided in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

123. Any comments on the assessment above?

124. It was possible to use the necessary medical kits correctly within the IDTM *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

125. Any comments on the assessment above?

126. The hypothesis "The patient can be attended and treated in real-time within critical incident." was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

127. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 16

Scenario description: Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 5 in hospitalization. Sudden electric shock due short circuit with flying sparks.

Hypothesis we are testing: The patient can be attended and evacuated out of the patient room to a safe area.

Success indicator: Critical incident is identified quickly. Patient is attended within adequate time. Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time. Medical Management kits are used correctly.

128. The critical incident could be identified and the patient was attended to quickly *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

129. Any comments on the assessment above?

130. Adequate treatment was able to be provided in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

131. Any comments on the assessment above?

132. The patient was able to be evacuated into the safe area in adequate time *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

133. Any comments on the assessment above?

134. The hypothesis "The patient can be attended and evacuated out of the patient room to a safe area." was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

135. Any comments on the assessment above?

Medical Scenario 17

Scenario description: Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X. She has low temperature, shivers, dysuria, back pain, has bradycardia, edema all over the body and difficulties in breathing. Oxygen saturation has dropped. The point of care lab results show high creatinine and high liver enzymes plus low albumine.

Hypothesis we are testing: Complex and severely sick patients can be identified and be treated with advanced machine supported procedures in the IDTM.

Success indicator: Acute kidney failure is identified by health personal by clinical and point of care lab diagnostics. Lab assessment and haemodialysis in IDTM is possible. Adequate space for the needed biomedical devices is available in the green area.

136. The acute kidney failure was identified by health personnel through clinical and point of care lab diagnostics *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

137. Any comments on the assessment above?

138. It was possible to conduct a lab assessment and haemodialysis in the IDTM. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

139. Any comments on the assessment above?

140. Adequate space was available for the needed biomedical devices in the green area *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

141. Any comments on the assessment above?

142. The hypothesis "Complex and severely sick patients can be identified and be treated with advanced machine supported procedures in the IDTM." was supported by this test. *

Strongly
Disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly
Agree

143. Any comments on the assessment above?

Logistics Scenario 1

Scenario description: The IDTM is stored in the warehouse and an alert is declared. A site has been identified and the team need to deploy with the IDTM. The team moves the IDTM from the warehouse to the set up site using maximum 2 open vans. The road ensure access by van up to 100 meters to the set up site.

Hypothesis we are testing: IDTM can be transported easily with limited transport means.

Success indicator: The IDTM can be moved easily.

144. The IDTM can be transported on any type of road, regardless of the means of transportation *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

145. Any comments on the assessment above?

146. The IDTM can be transported without vehicle assistance as far as needed *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

147. Any comments on the assessment above?

148. The IDTM can be divided into multiple parcels to allow easy transport, and be transportable by hand if needed *

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

149. Any comments on the assessment above?

150. The IDTM can resist extreme weather events and other phenomena during transport (e.g. waterproof, rodents, etc) *

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

151. Any comments on the assessment above?

152. The hypothesis "IDTM can be transported easily with limited transport means" was supported by this test. *

Strongly
Disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly
Agree

153. Any comments on the assessment above?

Logistics Scenario 2

Scenario description: The IDTM is available on the construction site. The team is requested to set it up and no instructions are provided. Nobody from the team has experience with the IDTM.

Hypothesis we are testing: The IDTM is easy to be erected/easy to be set up regardless of the use of manufacturer instructions.

Success indicator: The IDTM is correctly set up without manufacturer instructions within 4 hours.

154. The IDTM can be set up without manufacturer instructions *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

155. Any comments on the assessment above?

156. The IDTM can be set up without tools *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

157. Any comments on the assessment above?

158. The IDTM can be set up within 4 hours *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

159. Any comments on the assessment above?

160. The hypothesis "The IDTM is easy to be erected/easy to be set up regardless of the use of manufacturer instructions." was supported by this test. *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

161. Any comments on the assessment above?

Logistics Scenario 3

Scenario description: The MoH declare the end of the outbreak. The team needs to clean and disinfect the IDTM and make it ready for re-packing.

Hypothesis we are testing: The IDTM is easy to clean regardless of the use of manufacturer instructions.

Success indicator: The IDTM can be cleaned easily to acceptable clinical standard.

162. The IDTM can be easily cleaned *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

163. Any comments on the assessment above?

164. Water can be drained from the IDTM after cleaning *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

165. Any comments on the assessment above?

166. The hypothesis "The IDTM is easy to clean regardless of the use of manufacturer instructions." was supported by this test.

*

Strongly
Disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly
Agree

167. Any comments on the assessment above?

Logistics Scenario 4

Scenario description: The team is requested to dismantle and re-pack and no instructions are provided. Nobody from the team has experience with the IDTM

Hypothesis we are testing: The IDTM is easy to be dismantled and re-packed regardless of the use of manufacturer instructions.

Success indicator: The IDTM is correctly dismantled and re-packed without manufacturer instructions within half a day.

168. The IDTM can be dismantled and re-packed without manufacturer instructions *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

169. Any comments on the assessment above?

170. The IDTM can be dismantled and re-packed without tools *

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

171. Any comments on the assessment above?

172. The hypothesis "The IDTM is easy to be dismantled and re-packed regardless of the use of manufacturer instructions." was supported by this test.

*

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

173. Any comments on the assessment above?

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